

The Coupling Constant Equation and Quark Color

O Manor

May 4, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constant in its fourth representation, i.e. as a predictor of gauge field number, it is possible to extrapolate a reason for the quarks to differ in their color and a reason for their appearance only in three distinct colors. That is by using the fact that there are only two distinct elements. The 8- theory framework also predicts that there will be an interaction between bosons of different kind. The features of such interaction is currently unclear.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.1)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (2.2)$$

We are going to use the **forth representation** of the equation, i.e. as a predictor of the number of gauge fields for each interaction. In this representation, we correlate the right element of each interaction to the Number of gauge bosons or gauge fields. For example, the strong interaction has eight distinct gluon fields, in accordance to the eight.

$$\mathbf{8} + (1) \quad (2.3)$$

Weak interaction has three gauge fields – the W bosons and Z bosons. In Accordance to right oriented three within the bracket, marked in green.

$$((8 * \mathbf{3}) + (3)) + 3 \quad (2.4)$$

Same for the next elements in the series. In this paper, we are going to analyze only the first element, which represent the magnitude of the strong interaction. The strong interaction is mediated by two distinct elements; overall, we know that we have eight distinct gauge fields. We can represent the first term in the Series in the following way:

$$2^3 + (1) \quad (3)$$

So in order for those two distinct elements to create eight distinct gauge fields, They must differ; they must have a trait, which makes them distinct, the standard Model we associate a trait of so-called color. However, here we inferred color based on simple mathematics. In order of two distinct elements to create eight gauge fields, we need exactly three distinct kinds. Since those gauge bosons are different in their nature, there should be an interaction between the bosons themselves; it is currently unclear what would be the features of such an interaction, from distinct boson to another distinct boson. Analyzing such questions would lead us astray from the original paper, in which we tried to analyze why two fermions differ in a trait and appear in so-called three different colors.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)